

OVERCOMING THE DISADVANTAGES OF THE COAL INDUSTRY AS A SCIENTIFIC APPROACH TO GREENING CARBON ENERGY

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ABSTRACT. The problem of stopping carbon dioxide emissions from carbon energy can be solved either by ceasing coal mining or by overcoming the shortcomings of the coal industry. The main disadvantage of carbon energy is the emission of carbon dioxide from coal combustion. Carbon dioxide is also formed due to the endogenous oxidation of coal during its transportation. Eliminating carbon dioxide emissions from coal combustion can be achieved by forming an underground bifunctional mining and energy system containing except a steam generator with a steam turbine also several types of magnetohydrodynamic generators running by oxygen produced by algae on the earth's surface that eat carbon dioxide from the exhausted gases from coal combustion. Liquidation of endogenous oxidation of coal can be achieved by replacing wheeled transport with a new type of pipeline transport, using a carrier medium with superior density.

Key words: overcoming the shortcomings of the coal industry, doubling the coal thermal power plant efficiency, avoiding the endogenous oxidation of coal

Introduction

Global climate change is one of the major challenges to humankind today. It is manifested as extreme weather events treating human health, ecosystems, freshwater sources and water security, economies and society (IPCC, 2023).

Carbon dioxide emissions are one of the main causes of global climate change. Its concentrations in the atmosphere have risen by 50% compared to pre-industrial levels due to human activities, mainly fossil fuel burning and deforestation (Vandeginste et al., 2024).

In an effort to capture the CO₂ emissions from the anthropogenic sources or atmosphere, various methods have been developed such as use of amine and hydroxide-based absorption (Chai et al., 2022) or application of carbonate-based absorbents, especially calcium carbonate or limestone (Rau, 2011; Kirchner et al., 2020; Chai and Ngu, 2022). Limestone is used in a low-tech and inexpensive CO₂ capture process named the accelerated weathering of limestone (AWL) process (Chai et al., 2024).

The problem with amine and hydroxide-based absorption mainly comes from the intensive energy required to prepare and / or regenerate the utilized absorbents or lacking an effective way to handle their post-CO₂ absorption process. AWL process produces Ca(HCO₃)₂ that might be disposed into the ocean without much undesired consequence. However, at higher amounts disposed, this would cause saturation of the ocean with Ca(HCO₃)₂ and would drive the system towards an equilibrium which would adversely affect the CO₂ capture performance of the AWL process.

Carbon capture and storage or sequestration (CCS) using its electrochemical reduction to convert CO₂ into fuels and valuable chemicals, especially formic acid represents another proposed way to solve the problem (Duan-Mu et al., 2024; Devianto et al., 2024). However, finding suitable electrodes with high selectivity and efficiency, need of water and electricity and systems scaling up are among the main problems that have to be solved.

Enhanced weathering (EW) is a treatment method that involves accelerating the natural process of rock weathering by

spreading finely ground rocks over large areas, such as forest or agricultural land or coastal areas. It exhibits a minimal reliance on water resources compared to other CO₂ sequestration technologies (Kanzaki et al., 2022; Vandeginste et al., 2022).

Despite the promising results of EW, researchers draw attention to the importance of further investigation of the risks associated with EW, related to human health (Cobo et al., 2023) and changes in soil conditions that may favour the growth of certain plant species over others, and shifts in microbial diversity and abundance in soil (Crawford et al., 2020).

In addition, implementation of EW needs large-scale mining, grinding, and spreading operations, which involve dust generation that may cause health risks to workers (Taylor et al., 2016) and damage ecosystems (Cox and Edwards, 2019). Use of waste materials from rock mining and processing could be a solution but, in this case, a comprehensive analysis of its composition is needed and the material may be not always suitable for such applications.

According to some ideas, only the immediate replacement of carbon energy by green energy can save humanity from climate collapse.

Germany's latest steps to restart coal-fired energy generation, despite stunning progress in the country's use of renewable energy sources, indicate that, at least for the present, the society cannot continue further without this energy.

The two directions for the energy production compete with each other because of their disadvantages rather than their advantages. So, if energy generation by coal use is associated with carbon dioxide emissions, which makes it environmentally damaging, then the main complaint against green energy is its instability and susceptibility to the vagaries of the weather. In addition, the sun shines only during the day, and not every day, and the wind blows with different pressure and not always, there are also calms.

This paper aims at presenting a scientific approach to overcoming the disadvantages of energy production by using coal to directly generate electricity applying consequently

magnetohydrodynamic generator and turbogenerator in underground conditions. The magnetohydrodynamic generation runs by oxygen produced by algae on the earth's surface that eat carbon dioxide exhausted from coal combustion.

In addition, the paper describes the possibility to liquidate the endogenous oxidation of coal (and production of CO₂) achieved by replacing wheeled transport with a new type of pipeline transport.

Theoretical view of the problem of power plant efficiency

The presence of any shortcomings in themselves is not yet a basis for making a final verdict for declaring the winner technology, since shortcomings can be both surmountable and insurmountable. Hence, to answer the question about the potential competitiveness of these two ways of energy development, it is necessary to assess the surmountability of the shortcomings of each one.

In this sense, it is quite obvious that the main disadvantages of green energy cannot be overcome, since, no matter how successfully science develops, human civilisation will never be able to make the sun shine at night, and the wind blow with constant pressure and without calms, as well as even the most brilliant scientists clearly can't manage to increase the density of atmospheric air to the density of water or working vapour, so that wind generators could outdo hydraulic or vapour turbines in their power.

As for carbon dioxide emissions from coal energy, the significance of this shortcoming depends on a number of factors, and, first of all, on the level of thermodynamic perfecting of the operating cycle of a thermal power plant. To claim that modern thermal energy has already exhausted all its potential for perfecting is to sin against the truth. Figure 1 presents the energy balance diagram of a typical coal power plant (Alexandrov et al., 2006).

Fig. 1. Energy balance diagram of a typical coal power plant

As we can see, only 35 % of the energy released during the combustion of coal is converted into electricity. The lion's share of the combustion heat of coal is uselessly dissipated in the environment, causing only thermal pollution. In other words, only 35 % of the coal mined in a coal mine is consumed usefully, while 100 % of coal is completely burned, producing a volume of carbon dioxide three times greater than the emission that accompanies useful combustion.

Thus, if the efficiency of using coal combustion heat is increased to 70 %, the specific consumption of coal will be reduced by 2 times, which will lead to a double reduction in

carbon dioxide emissions into the atmosphere for every kWh of electricity generated.

Meanwhile, the efficiency of the Carnot's cycle is determined by the temperature difference between the high-temperature source (TH) and the low-temperature source (TL):

$$\eta = 1 - (TL/TH) \quad (1)$$

We cannot significantly lower the ambient temperature (TL). Hence, the main lever for increasing the efficiency of the thermodynamic cycle remains increasing the combustion temperature of coal (TH). The combustion temperature of coal depends on air parameters. Warm air is lighter than cold air, however, as atmospheric pressure increases, its density increases, which leads to an increase in its oxygen content (Bejan, 1997).

Now let's see how these parameters are interconnected with the geodetic mark of the location of the thermal power plant. When climbing mountains, atmospheric pressure drops. Along with a drop in atmospheric pressure, the density of the air decreases. However, the lower the air density, the lower its oxygen content. And vice versa, when descending into the mine, atmospheric pressure increases. At the same time, the density of the air increases, as does the oxygen content in it. Table 1 presents the air density at different geodetic marks.

Table 1. Air density at different geodetic marks*

Height, m	Air density, kg/m ³
- 1000	1,3476
- 500	1,2854
0	1,2250
500	1,1677
1000	1,1110

* [Engineering ToolBox](https://www.engineeringtoolbox.com) - Resources, Tools and Basic Information for Engineering and Design of Technical Applications. <https://www.engineeringtoolbox.com>

Let's assume that the most common thermal power plant is located at an altitude of 500 meters. From the point of view of an increase in the combustion temperature of coal, it is preferable to place an underground power unit in a mine at a depth of 1000 meters, where the density of the air supplied to the furnace is 15 % higher, as well as the oxygen content in it is also 15 % higher. Accordingly, the combustion of coal in this case will be accompanied by more intense heating of the flue gases, which will ensure a noticeable increase in the efficiency of such underground electricity generation.

The second factor indicating the thermodynamic benefit of burning coal underground is the increase in ambient temperature as the depth of the mine increases. As a rule, the temperature of rocks increases by 3.0 to 3.5 degrees Celsius for every 100 meters of immersion in a mine (Jones, 2018).

Thus, if the temperature on the earth's surface is 15 to 20 degrees Celsius, then at a depth of 1000 meters, the temperature of the rocks is 30 to 35 degrees higher. Consequently, supplying warm air with a temperature of 50 to 55 degrees Celsius to the furnace for burning coal also helps to heat the flue gases to a higher temperature, regardless of the season of year and time of day.

At the same time, to achieve even higher combustion temperatures, an increase in the oxygen content in the air by 15 % is clearly not enough. The use of concentrated oxygen is necessary. Then the coal combustion will produce high temperatures. When heated to such high temperatures

(2800...3000 degrees Celsius), intense ionization of gases occurs (Gupta et al., 2021). This effect can be further enhanced by injecting an ionizing additive such as potassium carbonate into this stream.

Now, all we have to do is correctly design, from a thermo-technical point of view, the thermodynamic cycle itself for utilizing the heat of the high-temperature flow of gases generated by burning coal in oxygen.

Thus, before supplying a stream of ionized gas to the steam generator, it is advisable to begin direct generation of electricity, passing this stream through a magnetohydrodynamic generator. Let us recall that according to Michael Faraday's law, when any charged particles cross magnetic field lines, an electromotive force is excited, which is the basis for the operation of magnetohydrodynamic generators.

However, producing oxygen through air liquefaction is a very energy-intensive process. Electricity consumption in this case is about 1.5 to 2.0 kWh per 1 m³ of oxygen gas (Ebrahimi et al, 2015).

An alternative way to produce oxygen from carbon dioxide, which is a product of coal combustion, is suggested by the Nature. This is the process of photosynthesis, thanks to which life exists on Earth.

However, in order to organise that the production of oxygen through photosynthesis has acquired an artificial character, concentrated carbon dioxide is necessary (Singh and Singh, 2014).

In other words, it is necessary to extract carbon dioxide from smoke emissions from coal combustion in concentrated form. Meanwhile, it should be emphasized that the most highly productive plants for processing carbon dioxide into oxygen are algae, while the resulting plant mass produced is quite comparable with tonnage of absorbed carbon dioxide (Clarens et al., 2010).

At the same time, the volumes of generated flue gases are so huge that to extract carbon dioxide from them, mass transfer equipment of very bulky dimensions will be required. Here, the gigantic vertical dimensions of the working underground space of mine shafts 1000 m deep can be used.

They are quite sufficient to accommodate absorption towers capable of completely freeing flue gases from the carbon dioxide they contain.

To sum up, the following main links in the technological chain of the coal industry can be built, capable of overcoming the main disadvantages of carbon energy:

1. Placement of the energy unit in underground conditions and at the greatest possible depth, since with increasing the depth, the air density increases and the oxygen content in it increases.

2. Coal combustion is carried out using oxygen coming from a battery of bio-transformers with algae, which convert carbon dioxide into plant matter and oxygen through solar radiation.

3. Electricity generation is carried out in two stages sequentially. At the first stage, magnetohydrodynamic generation occurs, while at the second stage a steam power cycle is used with heat transfer to the working fluid, which turns into steam, which rotates the turbogenerator.

4. The flue gases leaving the steam generator are freed from carbon dioxide by washing them in the absorption tower, which is equipped inside the mine shaft.

5. Carbon dioxide extracted from the absorption liquid in concentrated form is sent for conversion into plant mass and oxygen to bio-transformers.

As a result, the end-to-end efficiency of such a thermal power plant can be increased from 35...40 to 70...75%, which leads to a twofold reduction in carbon dioxide emissions into the atmosphere for every kWh of electricity.

Technical features of the formation of an underground coal power system

The essence of the developed technical solution is illustrated in Figures 2 and 3.

Before opening the deposit, the mine field is first cut into blocks 1 of a hexagonal shape, after which they are grouped together into regular three-lobed triads, in the centre of each there is a bush of four vertical shafts opening them.

Fig. 2. Scheme of cutting a mine field of a coal deposit when converting a mine to generate electricity: 1. Hexagonal blocks, 2. Main shaft, 3. Auxiliary shafts, 4. Radial cross-cuts, 5. By-pass cross-cuts

The centre of this bush is vertical workings - the main shaft 2, which is common to three adjacent hexagonal blocks 1. The main shaft 2 houses the power plant. The auxiliary vertical shafts 3 pass at the pairing node hexagons. Then horizontal mine workings 4 and 5 pass through the blocks - Figure 2. The underground steam power plant is located at the base of the main shaft 2. Before burning in the furnace 7, the coal is ground in a mill 6 - Figure 3. To achieve a combustion temperature of 2900...3000 degrees Celsius, coal is burned in a stream of oxygen produced by algae on the earth's surface.

High combustion temperature leads to ionization of flue gases. To increase the conductivity of the gas flow, a solution of potassium carbonate is injected into it. These highly-ionized gases are fed to magnetohydrodynamic generator 8 producing the first part of electric power of such underground thermal power unit - Figure 3.

Hot furnace gases, having passed through magnetohydrodynamic generator 8, come in steam generator 9, where the working medium of the steam-power cycle under an elevated pressure is transformed from liquid to vaporous state, under conditions of recuperated heat exchange. Instead of water, it is preferable to use low-melting metals with a low boiling point as the working fluid that boils in the steam generator 9 of such a thermodynamic cycle.

The list of those metals includes mercury, caesium, gallium, rubidium and sodium, as well as all kinds of their alloys. However, eutectic alloys can also be used, for example Wood's alloy (tin – 12.5 %; lead – 25.0 %; bismuth - 50 %, cadmium – 12.5 %, melting point 60°C, density - 9720 kg/m³).

The metal steam generated in the steam generator 9 is insufflated into the second magnetohydrodynamic generator 10, which extends along the entire height of the shaft in which the second part of the electricity is generated. When reaching the surface, a steam turbine 11 with a turbogenerator 12 is installed, running on metal steam, generating a third part of the electricity. The metal steam expanded in the turbine 11 is again liquefied in the condenser 13, and flows into the liquid metal magnetohydrodynamic generator 21, in which the movement of this vertical flow of liquid metal generates the fourth part of electricity. The hydrostatic pressure of this vertical column of liquid metal is converted by hydraulic turbine 22 into an additional volume of electricity, being already the fifth portion in such an underground thermodynamic cycle - Figure 3.

The flow of liquid metal leaving the hydraulic turbine 22 again enters the steam generator 9 for boiling. Thus, the liquid metal circulation cycle is completely closed - Figure 3.

A twofold increase in the completeness of conversion of the combustion heat of coal into electricity also halves the specific carbon dioxide emissions for each kWh of electricity generated. However, this does not completely eliminate the emission of carbon dioxide into the atmosphere. Meanwhile, the kilometre depth of the mine shaft allows this hollow cylinder to be turned into a giant scrubber to completely absorb the carbon dioxide produced by burning coal.

Before extracting carbon dioxide, flue gases leaving the steam generator 9 are subjected to cleaning from dust in dry cyclone 14 and electric precipitator 15. The furnace gases, cleared of dust, are washed in the absorption tower 16 by monoethanolamine, which is a selective carbon dioxide

sorbent. As a result, gas exhaust from coal combustion, drawn out by fan 17, is ejected through chimney 18 in a state purified from carbon dioxide - Figure 3.

To regenerate the liquid sorbent, the solution of carbon dioxide in monoethanolamine leaving the absorption tower 16 is heated by the heat of condensation of the liquid metal in the condenser 13. In this case, pure carbon dioxide is desorbed from such a hot liquid and supplied for compression to an underground reception system consisting of wells 23, 29 and underground storage 30 - Figure 3.

Further, through a network of gas distribution pipelines 31, this gas is supplied to transparent biotransformers 32, illuminated by the sun, installed on the earth's surface, filled with microalgae *Spirulina plantensis* (Jung et al., 2019; Branyikova and Lucakova, 2021). A vertical tubular photobioreactor is shown as an example in Figure 4.

Oxygen, produced in solar biotransformers 32, is sent further through pipeline 33 to underground storage 34, from which it is supplied for combustion of solid fuel into furnace 7. At the same time, from every 1.83 kilograms of carbon dioxide, 1 kilogram of high-calorie plant combustible material is formed (in terms of dry matter) - Figure 3.

This artificial brushwood can be dried and burned in the same firebox 7. However, the same crop can be used to produce biofuel or added to livestock feed. As we can see, solar radiation can be used not only for direct conversion into electricity by photocells, but also aimed at converting carbon dioxide into plant fuel and oxygen using algae.

The use of oxygen makes it possible to increase the temperature of coal combustion, which makes it possible to include magnetodynamic generators in the thermodynamic cycle of electricity production. Thus, algae can green the coal energy, creating the environmentally friendly coal industry.

Steps to avoid the endogenous oxidation of coal

A very significant contribution to carbon dioxide emissions is made not only by the combustion of coal at thermal power plants, but also by the processes of transporting and storing coal. Approximately 15...20 % of the total carbon dioxide emissions are due to the uncontrolled emission of carbon dioxide from the invisible so-called endogenous oxidation of coal, contacting with air oxygen during its transportation and storage in the open air.

According to integral data from the quality control departments of all coal mining enterprises of the former Soviet Union, the weighted average calorific value of 1 kg of shipped solid fuel supplied to power engineers was 5050 kcal.

Meanwhile, according to the consolidated reporting data of all thermal power plants in the country, the weighted average calorific value of thermal coals supplied to the furnaces of steam boilers at thermal power facilities was, on average, equal to 3833 kcal/kg (Rzhevsky, 1990)..

Is it realistic to purely technologically eliminate this "minor drawback" lying on the surface, which is responsible for every fifth ton of carbon dioxide emitted into the atmosphere by the most unauthorized, i.e. in a purely latent way? It turns out, yes. To do this, it is enough to isolate the material from its contact with air oxygen, at all stages of its movement, starting with the extraction of coal from the seam, and ending with storage at the place of its use.

Fig. 3. A schematic diagram of an underground thermal power unit located at the base of the main shaft 2 and interconnected with gas-cleaning equipment and ground-surface algae farming: 6. Mill, 7. Furnace, 8. First MHD-generator, 9. Steam generator, 10. Second MHD-generator, 11. Steam turbine, 12. Turbogenerator, 13. Boiler, 14. Dry cyclone, 15. Electric filter, 16. Absorption tower, 17. Smoke exhauster, 18. Chimney, 19. Reservoir, 20. Pump, 21. Third MHD-generator, 22. Hydro Turbine, 23, 29 Blind wells, 24. Evaporator, 25. Vapour pipeline, 26. Condenser, 27. Tank, 28, 31, 33. Pipelines, 30. Underground carbon dioxide storage, 32. Algae grower, 34. Underground oxygen storage

Fig. 4. Tubular photobioreactor - general view

The problem solution is suggested by nature itself, which “invented” a method of transporting solid materials using a carrier medium with superior density - for example, operating like timber rafting on rivers. Therefore, to adopt this godsend from nature, we only had to prepare an artificial carrier medium on a water-salt basis with a given set of physical, sanitary, hygienic and environmental properties and find a simple and non-energy-intensive procedure for its complete regeneration from the surface of lump coal delivered to destination (Brodt, 2023).

Thus, this “heavy water” is practically not consumed in such a transport cycle, but only circulates in a closed loop between an open coal mine (an underground coal mine) and the place where coal is burned. Moreover, the idle branch is also not left without work, along it, ash and slag waste returns in the same flow way to the place of coal mining and goes to the backfill of the mined-out space - Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Principled flow-sheet transport services for a coal power plant by new type of hydraulic transport using Archimedes' law

Of course, the load on the idle branch is less than on the working one. To eliminate such “discrimination,” this same “parasitic” transport artery can be used to deliver household waste from urban cities to its burial site instead of transporting it to landfills.

Testing such an environmentally friendly transport cycle in a pilot format quite clearly convinces that no one has yet cancelled Archimedes' law, and, if we expand the scope of its

application for transport purposes, the contribution of coal energy to emissions carbon dioxide due to the refusal to use wheeled vehicles, which also suffer from high cyclical operation and their own carbon dioxide emissions, is reduced by at least 15...20 %.

Conclusion

The main disadvantages of carbon energy can be eliminated if we use the achievements of such sciences as mining, thermodynamics, physics, chemistry, metallurgy and biology.

At the same time, it turns out that environmentally friendly systems for generating electricity by burning coal are technically unfeasible under earth's surface condition.

Increasing the level of energy perfection of the thermodynamic cycle itself by increasing the efficiency from 35 to 70 % can be achieved by including magnetohydrodynamic generators in an underground system. This provides the lion's share of the reduction in carbon dioxide emissions per each kWh of electricity generated.

The formed flow of carbon dioxide is extracted from the flue gases in a giant scrubber located along the entire height of the mine shaft. After desorption from the liquid sorbent, the flow of pure carbon dioxide is consumed by algae enclosed in bio-transformers illuminated by solar radiation. The oxygen released by algae is supplied to the combustion of coal, which makes it possible to achieve flue gas temperatures sufficient for the operation of magnetohydrodynamic power generation systems.

The elimination of endogenous oxidation of coal during its transportation can be achieved by isolating coal from atmospheric oxygen when delivering coal by a new type of pipeline hydraulic transport, in which pieces of coal of any size drift in a carrier medium with a density exceeding their density.

The proposed two technological approaches are more difficult and challenging scientific task than stopping coal mining worldwide by 2050. However, they are achievable. By combining their efforts, modern science and technology will be able to create environmentally friendly carbon energy project by 2050.

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